

Einstein's Equation

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Abstract

According to the principle of the general relativity theory, the gravity field equation should contain the field energy as a source of the field itself. Including the field energy-momentum tensor into the Einstein's equation brings extra unknown quantities to the equation. Such equation is not suitable for a metric finding; however it allows – based on the known metric – calculating the whole energy-momentum tensor of both matter and gravitational field. As the gravity field metric, the metric of continuous field can be used, parameters of which are found from the generally covariant one-parametric equation. Here, the solutions are given of the equation for the spherically symmetric stationary problem. One of the solutions coincides practically with that by Schwarzschild for weak fields, while the other one describes an expulsive field.

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1. Introduction

More often than not, the general relativity theory is meant to be identifiable with the Einstein's equation. Indeed, the gravitational field equation allows finding the metrical tensor g_{ik} defining an acceleration field having an effect on both matter and fields. The Einstein's equation looks like as follows:

$$G_{ik} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{ik}, \quad (1)$$

where, T_{ik} is tensor of energy-momentum-tensions of a matter including an electromagnetic field. To this equation, Einstein came through a long way of doubts, trials and errors [1]. Therewith Einstein had to sacrifice the general relativity theory initial principle, which was put forward as long ago as in 1913 [2]. According to this principle, energy of a gravity field (more precisely, of its energy-momentum tensor) is a source of the field itself. In this regard, Einstein noticed [2]:

“One can see that along with components of energy-tensions tensor of the matter T_{ik} as full-valued sources of a field, also components of the tensor of gravity field act (namely θ_{ik}); apparently, this requirement is necessary as a gravitational action of a system cannot depend on a physical nature of the energy acting as the field source.” [2]

2. Development

The equation (1) describes perfectly the known empiric data; however this fact does not allow absolutizing it as some scientists are inclined to do. To the approximate nature of the Einstein's equation, an attention is paid extremely seldom. Perhaps, only Landau and Lifshitz paid the due attention to this circumstance. While deriving the Einstein's equation in their famous course “Einstein's Equations” ([3], Art. 95), they observed as follows,

“The gravitational interaction plays the role only for bodies with big enough mass (due to the smallness of the gravitational constant). That is why, while investigating a gravity

field, we used to deal with macroscopic bodies” [3],

which serves as a pretext for use of the macroscopic tensor of energy-momentum in the equation (1). This affirmation must be fair in the case of relatively small gravity fields.

Is this true?

An energy density of a gravity field is not hard to be determined based on the Newtonian law of gravitation. It coincides with energy density in the second approximation of the general relativity theory and has the value $-\frac{g^2}{8\pi G}$ [3]. The obtained-here from mass density provides with a correction to the Newtonian law of gravitation. The simplest calculations [4] bring us to the law of gravitation

$$-\frac{Gm}{r^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{Gm}{c^2 r}} \approx -\frac{Gm}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 2\frac{Gm}{c^2 r}}}, \quad (2)$$

Asymptotically equal to the law of gravitation obtained from the Schwarzschild metric (the expression in the right side). Definitely, such approach cannot compete with the solutions obtained from the Einstein's equation. However this is a serious reason to put in doubt an applicability of the Einstein's equation solutions to discretionary fields.

It looks quite tempting to enter energy of a gravity field into the equation (1):

$$G_{ik} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \Theta_{ik}, \quad (3)$$

where Θ_{ik} is already complete tensor of energy-momentum-tensions embracing the energy-momentum tensor of a gravity field. Exactly this version of the gravity field equation was considered by Einstein as the main one (during almost two years). On one hand, the field “energy tensor” was needed for conservation laws fulfillment; on the other hand, such member entering made the equation non-covariant.

There exists one more circumstance, which Einstein guessed for sure. In the electrodynamics, energy is a function of field intensity. There are no reasons to

think that in the gravity theory, something will be different. That is why we shall presume that the energy-momentum tensor of a gravity field is the function of the metrical tensor. Then, the unknown values will take place in both left and right sides of the equation (3) and besides, the unknown values number will exceed the equations number. This makes the equation (3) useless.

Figure 1. Changes of space-time scales along a geodesic line of a homogeneous field.

We have no excuses for doubts in the correctness of the expression (3), however at the same time, we are not able use it as an equation. Nevertheless, if we know a metrical tensor, we can calculate the whole tensor of energy-momentum, which contains such gravity field tensor $\Theta_{ik} = \theta_{ik}$ where

$$\Theta_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} G_{ik},$$

and θ_{ik} is the field energy-momentum tensor for an empty space.

Thus now, the Einstein's equation corresponds precisely to the principles of the general relativity theory². Along with it, the equation acquired absolutely another sense.

²This version of the gravity field equation was the one, which was considered by Einstein from the very beginning [2] (1913) as the most preferable one. Einstein abandoned it only in 1915. Unexceptionally, any attempts of θ_{ik} calculation based on the conservation law led to a non-covariant equation. The problem was solved only after exclusion of θ_{ik} from the equation.

Nevertheless in the case of such approach again, the necessity arises to find the gravity field equation, i.e. the equation for the metrical tensor.

Our approach is based on finding of a possible form of metrics of a continuous field. Notice that if we would select a space area with a specific size δ , then in the limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$, the field inside of this area is homogeneous³. Herewith the conclusion can be made that the metric of a continuous field in the limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$ is homogeneous. The metric of the homogeneous field [5] with the acceleration (of free fall) α in the direction x is

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2\alpha x}{c^2}} (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2). \quad (4)$$

The acceleration in every fixed point in this reference system is constant:

$$\frac{d^2 x^i}{dt^2} = -c^2 \Gamma_{00}^i = const.$$

A metric of any continuous field is a subsequence of infinitesimal metrics (4), see Fig. 1. That is why regardless of a nature of a continuous field⁴, it's any metric should have the form:

$$ds^2 = \exp(2\psi) \eta_{ik} dx_i dx_k. \quad (5)$$

where ψ is a continuous function of position coordinates and η_{ik} is a linear element of a flat space.

The metric of the general form (5) forms an additive group on ψ , i.e. a summation of parameters of the metric $\psi_1 + \psi_2$ of the form (5) leads to the metric of the same form. This brings us to the affirmation that the equation describing the parameter ψ must be linear. The simplest generally covariant equation being in accord with the correspondence principles looks like

$$\square \psi = -4\pi GT. \quad (6)$$

where scalar $T = T_{ii}$.

Resolving of Schwarzschild problem gives the solution, essential Christoffel symbols of which are asymptotically equal to Christoffel symbols of Schwarzschild metric.

³Consequence of the definition of function continuity.

⁴We restricted ourselves to the case of homogeneous space.

Figure 2. Two stationary solutions of a spherically symmetric field. The green line is intensity of a field, source of which is the field itself. The black line is intensity of a field of a point source. The grey line is the field of the Schwarzschild solution.

Figure 3. “Bubble Nebula”. Quite probably that the dust cloud in vicinity of the bubble is heated up by particles accelerated by expulsive field. Image Credit & Copyright: J-P Metsävainio (Astro Anarchy).

The gravitation law for a point source $-\frac{GM}{r^2} e^{\frac{GM}{c^2 r}}$ in area of strong fields is distinct from the law given by the Schwarzschild metric $-\frac{GM}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2GM/(rc^2)}}$. However here we see that there is fulfilled the stronger correspondence principle – namely the correspondence to the solutions of the Einstein’s equation.

An unexpected spherically symmetric solution is represented by a stationary field, where a matter is absent at all.

Expulsive proof masses see the Figures (2) and (3).

Some details can be found in [6, 7].

3. Conclusions

We see that a metric of a general form does not make us a choice. It is necessary to replace the Einstein equation by another. The equation itself connects the metric with the energy-momentum-tension tensor.

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